

Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrum Analysis of Volatile Components of Methanolic Leaves Extract of *Cordia Myxa*

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have been used to treat human diseases for thousands of years because they have vast and diverse assortment of organic compounds that can produce a definite physiological action on the human body. The objectives of this study were analysis of the secondary metabolite products of methanolic leaf extract of *Cordia myxa*. The identification of bioactive chemical compounds is based on the peak area, retention time molecular weight and molecular formula. GC-MS analysis of *Cordia myxa* revealed the existence of the 2-[3-Cyclohexylaminopropylamino] ethylthiophosphate, Spiro[2.4]heptan-4-one, D-Glucose, 6-O- α -Dgalactopyranosyl, ϵ -N-Formyl-L-lysine, Dodecanoic acid, 3-hydroxy, Paromomycin, 2,5-Dimethyl-4-hydroxy-3(2H)-furanone, 10-Methyl-E-11-tridecen-1-ol propionate, 1,3-Dioxolane, 4-[[2-methoxy-4-octadecenyl]oxy]methyl]-2,2, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural, 6-Acetyl- β -d-mannose, E-9-Methyl-8-tridecen-2-ol, acetate, 4-Hexenal, 6-hydroxy-4-methyl-, dimethyl acetal, acetate, (Z, α -D-Glucopyranoside, O- α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1.fwdarw.3)- β , 2-Cyclohexylpiperidine, Dodecanoic acid, 3-hydroxy, Cyclopentadecanone, 2-hydroxy, Ethyl iso-allocholate, 3-O-Methyl-d-glucose, 13-Heptadecyn-1-ol, Trans-13-Octadecenoic acid, Dasycarpidan-1-methanol, acetate (ester, 5H-Cyclopropa[3,4]benz[1,2-e]azulen-5-one, 9-(acetyloxy)-3, α -Tocopheryl acetate.

Keywords: *Cordia myxa*, Chemical analysis, GC-MS, Products, Secondary metabolite.

INTRODUCTION

Plants are rich source of secondary metabolites with various biological activities^{1,2}. The chemical compounds present in the plant should be analyzed not only for discovery of drugs but also for identifying new phytocompounds for the synthesis of complex substance and to discover the actual remedies (*Cordia myxa* fruit locally known as "Bumber" is one of the largest genera in the family Boragiaceae, as about 300 species have been identified worldwide mostly in warmer region³⁻⁵. *C. myxa* is a sweet fruit because it contains the maximum amount of sucrose, glucose, fructose and high total dietary fiber, which plays one important role in decreasing risk of many diseases, *C. myxa* fruits are a rich source of proteins, carbohydrates, ash, fat and essential minerals⁶⁻¹¹. Medical plants are very important in our daily life as these are used for the treatment of many diseases. *C. myxa* contained various compounds which are responsible for protection against pathogenesis. Recently, there are trends for using plants in therapy (back to the nature) as a result of side effects and complications of chemotherapies. *C. myxa* is used in popular folk medicine as abortive in tropical region of the world Analgesic and as inflammatory agents in both acute and chronic phase¹². Chromatography is a separation technique in which a mobile phase carrying the mixture is moved through a selective absorbent stationary phase. It is a technique for quality control and standardization of phyto components. Gas chromatography involves the principle

of adsorption and partition, is an important tool for separation of volatile compounds. Medicinal plants are directly analyzed for their existing compounds by GC-MS technique. It is mainly used for the determination of thermochemical constants, for purification of compounds and for qualitative and quantitative analysis of mixtures. Few reports are available on the pharmacological properties of the plant. The fruit of *C. myxa* is popularly used for the treatment of chest, urinary tract infections, diseases of the lung and spleen analgesic, anti-inflammatory cytotoxic, antiviral, antiulcer, anticancer, antihelminthic and anti-HIV-1¹³⁻¹⁶. Mucilage extract of *C. myxa* was shown to be active against promastigotes of *Leishmania major* and *L. infantum*¹⁷. The present study has been undertaken to investigate the bioactive compounds present in methanolic leaves extract of *Cordia myxa*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant material, extraction and isolation of Cordia myxa

Cordia myxa leaves were collected from Hilla city, middle of Iraq. *Cordia myxa* was washed with sterile distilled water and shade dried. The leaves were powdered and stored in an air tight container at room temperature. Methanolic leaves extract of *Cordia myxa* powdered were soaked in 500 mL methanol for 14 hours in a rotatory shaker. The filtrates were used for further phytochemical analysis¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Table 1: Bioactive chemical compounds identified in methanolic extract of *Cordia myxa*.

<p>D-Glucose,6-O-α-Dgalactopyranosyl- RT=3.545 Mw=342.11621 Pharmacological activity: Anti-carcinogenic</p>		
<p>2,5-Dimethyl-4-hydroxy-3(2H)-furanone RT=4.563 Mw=128.047344 Pharmacological activity: Antioxidant</p>		
<p>1,3-Dioxolane, 4-[[2-methoxy-4-octadecenyl]oxy]methyl]-2,2 RT=5.210 Mw=412.35526 Pharmacological activity: antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activity</p>		
<p>E-9-Methyl-8-tridecen-2-ol, acetate RT=7.807 Mw=254.22458 Pharmacological activity: anti-malarial, anti-allergy</p>		

antioxidant

4-Hexenal , 6-hydroxy-4-methyl- ,
dimethyl acetal , acetate ,(Z)
RT=7.836
Mw=216.136159
Pharmacological activity:
Anti-bacterial, Antifungal Activity

α -D-Glucopyranoside , O- α -D-
glucopyranosyl-(1.fwdarw.3)- β
RT=8.139
Mw=504.169035
Pharmacological activity:
anti-inflammatory

2-Cyclohexylpiperidine
RT=8.820
Mw=167.167399
Pharmacological activity:
anti-inflammatory agent

Dodecanoic acid , 3-hydroxy-
RT=9.181
Mw=216.1725445
Pharmacological activity:
anti-HIV activity

Cyclopentadecanone ,2-hydroxy-
RT=9.701
Mw=240.20893
Pharmacological activity:
anti-inflammatory and *Anti* cancer

Ethyl iso- allocholate
RT=13.564
Mw=436.318874
Pharmacological activity:
Antioxidant

3-O-Methyl-d-glucose
RT=15.486
Mw=194.079039
Pharmacological activity:
anti-cancer, anti inflammatory

13-Heptadecyn-1-ol
RT=16.556
Mw=252.245316
Pharmacological activity:
anti- inflammatory *activity*

Trans-13-Octadecenoic acid
RT=16.608
Mw=282.25588
Pharmacological activity:
anti-inflammatory activity

Dasycarpidan-1-methanol , acetate
(ester)
RT=18.176
Mw=326.199429
Pharmacological activity:
antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-
inflammatory

α -Tocopheryl acetate
RT=25.740
Mw=472.391645
Pharmacological activity:
Anti-Inflammatory and Analgesic
activity

Figure 1: GC-MS chromatogram of methanolic extract of *Cordia myxa*.

Gas chromatography – mass spectrum analysis

The Gas chromatography – mass spectrum analysis of methanolic extract of *Cordia myxa* was made in a (Agilent 789 A) instrument under computer control at 70 eV. About 1 μ L of the methanol extract was injected into the GC-MS using a micro syringe and the scanning was done for 45 minutes. The time from when the injection was made (Initial time) to when elution occurred referred to as the Retention time (RT). While the instrument was run, the computer generated a graph from the signal called Chromatogram. Each of the peaks in the chromatogram represented the signal created when a compound eluted from the Gas chromatography column into the detector²⁰⁻³¹. The M/Z (mass / charge) ratio obtained was calibrated from the graph obtained, which was called as the Mass spectrum graph which is the fingerprint of a molecule. Before analyzing the extract using gas chromatography and mass spectroscopy, the temperature of the oven, the flow rate of the gas used and the electron gun were programmed initially. The identity of the components in the extracts was assigned by the comparison of their retention indices and mass spectra fragmentation patterns with those stored on the computer library and also with published literatures. Compounds were identified by comparing their spectra to those of the Wiley and NIST/EPA/NIH mass spectral libraries³²⁻⁴⁰.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of phytochemical compounds

GC-MS is a powerful technique used for many applications which has very high sensitivity and

specificity. GC-MS analysis of compounds was carried out in methanolic extract of *Cordia myxa*, shown in Table 1. The GC-MS chromatogram of the 23 peaks of the compounds detected was shown in Figure 1. The set up peak were determined to be 2-[3-Cyclohexylaminopropylamino]ethylthiophosphate, Spiro[2.4]heptan-4-one, D-Glucose, 6-O- α -Dgalactopyranosyl, ϵ -N-Formyl-L-lysine, Dodecanoic acid, 3-hydroxy, Paromomycin, 2,5-Dimethyl-4-hydroxy-3(2H)-furanone, 10-Methyl-E-11-tridecen-1-ol propionate, 1,3-Dioxolane, 4-[(2-methoxy-4-octadecenyl)oxy]methyl]-2,2, 5-Hydroxymethylfurfural, 6-Acetyl- β -D-mannose, E-9-Methyl-8-tridecen-2-ol, acetate, 4-Hexenal, 6-hydroxy-4-methyl-, dimethyl acetal, (Z, α -D-Glucopyranoside, O- α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1.fwdarw.3)- β , 2-Cyclohexylpiperidine, Dodecanoic acid, 3-hydroxy, Cyclopentadecanone, 2-hydroxy, Ethyl iso-allocholate, 3-O-Methyl-d-glucose, 13-Heptadecyn-1-ol, Trans-13-Octadecenoic acid, Dasycarpidan-1-methanol, acetate (ester, 5H-Cyclopropa[3,4]benz[1,2-e]azulen-5-one, 9-(acetyloxy)-3, α -Tocopheryl acetate. Phytochemicals present in herbal medicinal plants, spices, vegetables and fruits have a protective role against many diseases⁴¹⁻⁴⁸. They also inhibit oxidation process through a variety of mechanism and they act as radical scavengers. Quantitative assay for the presence of plant phytochemical analysis of *C. myxa* indicated the presence of restively high levels of glycosides, flavonoids, sterols, saponins, trepenoids, alkaloids, phenolic acids, gums and mucilage. The fruit of *C. myxa* is used for treatment of chest, urinary infection, disease of the lung and spleen and against liver

fibrosis when measured level of hepatic enzymes ALT, ALP, AST¹². Antiradical activity was measured, it contain 40/100g of scorbic acid and antioxidant of *C. myxa* which may be due phenols, scorbic acid and lycopene¹³. Most important of such compounds are alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins and phenolic compounds^{49,50}. Pharmacists are interested in these compounds because of their therapeutic performance and low toxicity¹. A number of such compounds have been isolated from plants which could be used for the development of new drugs to inhibit the growth of bacterial and fungal pathogens and to quench ROS with possibly novel mechanisms of action and low toxicity to the host cell⁵¹⁻⁵⁸.

CONCLUSION

Twenty three bioactive chemical constituents have been identified from methanolic extract of the *Cordia myxa* by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry technique. Secondary metabolite products of *Cordia myxa* forms a primary platform for further pharmacological investigation for the development of new potential anti-insect compounds.

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REFERENCES

- Inayatullah S, Prenzler PD, Obied HK, Rehman AU, Mirza B. Bioprospect-ing traditional Pakistani medicinal plants for potent antioxidants. *Food Chem.* 2012; 132: 222–229.
- Ahmad I, Aqil F. In vitro efficacy of bioactive extracts of 15 medicinal plants against ESBL-producing multidrug-resistant enteric bacteria. *Microbiol. Res.* 2007; 162: 264–275.
- Aberoumand A, Deokule SS. Assessment of the nutritional Value of plant-based diets in relation to human carbohydrates: A preliminary study. *Adv. J. Food Sci. Technol.* 2010; 2(1): 1-5.
- Aberoumand A. Preliminary evaluation of some phytochemical and nutrients constituents of Iranian *Cordia myxa* fruits. *Int. J. Agric. Food Sci.* 2011; 1(2): 30-33.
- Pandey B, Deshpande B, Singh S, Chandrakar V. Estimation of elemental contents of *Cordia myxa* and its antimicrobial activity against various pathogenic microorganisms. *Ind. J. Sci. Res.* 2014; 4(1): 39-44.
- Ranjbar M, Varzi HN, Sabbagh A, Bolooki A, Sazman A. Study on analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties of *Cordia myxa* fruit hydroalkaloid extract. *Pak. J. Biol. Sci.* 2013; 16(24): 2066- 2069.
- Costa JF, David JP, David JM, Giulietti AM, Queiroz LP, Santos RR, Soares MB. Immunomodulatory activity of extracts from *Cordia superba* Cham. and *Cordia rufescens* A. DC. (Boraginaceae), plant species native from Brazilian Semi-arid. *Braz. J. Pharmacog.* 2008; 18(1): 11 - 15.
- Moghimpour E, Aghel N, Adelpour A. Formation and characterization of oral mucoadhesive chlorhexidine tablets using *Cordia myxa* mucilage. *Jundishapur J. Nat. Pharmacet. Products.* 2012; 7(14): 129-133.
- Moustafa SM, Menshawi BM, Wassel GM, Mahmoud K, Mounier MM. Screening of some plants in Egypt for their cytotoxicity against four human cancer cell lines. *Int. J. Pharm. Tech. Res.* 2014; 6(3): 1074-1084.
- Rashed K, Luo TM, Zhang LT, Zheng YT. Evaluation of anti-HIV-1 activity of *Cordia myxa* L. and phytochemical profile. *Banat's J. Biotechnol.* 2014; 9: 51-56.
- Saki J, Khademvatan S, Pazyar N, Eskandari A, Tamoradi A, Nazari P. In Vitro Activity of *Cordia myxa* Mucilage Extract Against *Leishmania major* and *L. infantum* Promastigotes. *Jundishapur J Microbiol.* 2015; 8(3): e19640.
- Afzal M, Obuekwe C, Khan AR, Barakat, H. Influence of *Cordia myxa* on chemically induced oxidative stress. *Nutr. Food Sci.* 2009; 39 (1): 6-15.
- Kachhwaha P, Gehlot HS. Changes in phytonutrients and antioxidant properties of *Cordia myxa* and *Carissa carandas* fruit during ripening. *Ind. J. Plant Physiol.* 2015; 20(1): 72-78.
- Jawaid T, Shukla D, Verma J. Anti-inflammatory activity of the plants used in traditional medicines. *Int. J. Biomed. Res.* 2011; 2(4): 252-263.
- Malik M, Ahmad R. Determination of phenolic and flavonoid contents of ethanolic extract of Kanunang leaves (*Cordia myxa* L.). *Int. J. PharmTech Res.* 2015; 7(2): 243-246.
- Jagzap RK, Nirmal SA, Kadam SK. Potential of *Ficus racenosa* bark: an immunomodulatory agent. *Ind. J. Basic Appl. Med. Res.* 2012; 1(2): 120-127.
- Rahami-Esboei B, Ghobani A, Cholami SH, Azadbakht M, Ziaei H, Taghavi M. Antiparasitic effects of *Allium paradoxum* as a conventional consumed vegetable. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res.* 2014; 8(31): 2979-2983.
- Kadhim MJ, Sosa AA, Hameed IH. Evaluation of anti-bacterial activity and bioactive chemical analysis of *Ocimum basilicum* using Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) techniques. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(6): 127-146.
- Mohammed GJ, Kadhim MJ, Hussein HM. Characterization of bioactive chemical compounds from *Aspergillus terreus* and evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activity. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research.* 2016; 8(6): 889-905.
- Hameed IH, Altameme HJ, Idan SA. Artemisia annua: Biochemical products analysis of methanolic aerial parts extract and anti-microbial capacity. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences.* 2016; 7(2): 1843- 1868
- Hussein AO, Mohammed GJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical screening of methanolic dried galls extract of *Quercus infectoria* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and

- Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 49-59.
22. Sosa AA, Bagi SH, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Euphorbia lathyris* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 109-126.
23. Altameme HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Phytochemical analysis of *Urtica dioica* leaves by fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(10): 238-252.
24. Mohammed GJ, Omran AM, Hussein HM. Antibacterial and Phytochemical Analysis of *Piper nigrum* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrum and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(6): 977-996.
25. Hamza LF, Kamal SA, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Penicillium expansum* and evaluating antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(9): 194-220.
26. Jasim H, Hussein AO, Hameed IH, Kareem MA. Characterization of alkaloid constitution and evaluation of antimicrobial activity of *Solanum nigrum* using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(4): 56-72.
27. Hadi MY, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Nigella sativa* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 8-24.
28. Hameed IH, Ibraheem IA, Kadhim HJ. Gas chromatography mass spectrum and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis of methanolic extract of *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (6): 90-106.
29. Shareef HK, Muhammed HJ, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Antibacterial effect of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) roscoe and bioactive chemical analysis using gas chromatography mass spectrum. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 20-40.
30. Al-Jassaci MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. Secondary Metabolites Analysis of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and Evaluation of Antibacterial Activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 2016; 8(5): 304-315.
31. Mohammed GJ, Al-Jassani MJ, Hameed IH. Antibacterial, Antifungal Activity and Chemical analysis of *Punica grantanum* (Pomegranate peel) using GC-MS and FTIR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 480-494.
32. Al-Marzoqi AH, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Determination of metabolites products by *Cassia angustifolia* and evaluate antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(2): 25-48.
33. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Abu-Serag NA. Analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of two medicinal plants, *Equisetum arvense* and *Alchemilla vulgaris* seed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Malays. Appl. Biol*. 2015; 44(4): 47-58.
34. Hameed IH, Hamza LF, Kamal SA. Analysis of bioactive chemical compounds of *Aspergillus niger* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015;7(8): 132-163.
35. Hameed IH, Hussein HJ, Kareem MA, Hamad NS. Identification of five newly described bioactive chemical compounds in methanolic extract of *Mentha viridis* by using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7 (7): 107-125.
36. Hussein HM, Hameed IH, Ibraheem OA. Antimicrobial Activity and spectral chemical analysis of methanolic leaves extract of *Adiantum Capillus-Veneris* using GC-MS and FT-IR spectroscopy. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016; 8(3): 369-385.
37. Hussein HJ, Hadi MY, Hameed IH. Study of chemical composition of *Foeniculum vulgare* using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer and gas chromatography - mass spectrometry. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2016; 8(3): 60-89.
38. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hameed IH. *In vitro* antibacterial, antifungal and phytochemical analysis of methanolic fruit extract of *Cassia fistula*. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*. 2016; 32(2): 10-30.
39. Altameme HJ, Hameed IH, Idan SA, Hadi MY. Biochemical analysis of *Origanum vulgare* seeds by fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytotherapy*. 2015; 7(9): 221-237.
40. Hussein HM. Determination of phytochemical composition and ten elements content (CD, CA, CR, CO, FE, PB, MG, MN, NI AND ZN) of *CARDARIA DRABA* by GC-MS, FT-IR and AAS technique. *Int. J Pharm Bio Sci*. 2016; 7(3): (B) 1009 –1017.
41. Hussein HM. Analysis of trace heavy metals and volatile chemical compounds of *Lepidium sativum* using atomic absorption spectroscopy, gas chromatography-mass spectrometric and fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016; 7(4): 2529 – 2555.
42. Hameed IH. A new polymorphic positions discovered in mitochondrial DNA hypervariable region HVIII from central and north-central of Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA*. 2016; 27(5): 3250-4.
43. Jaddoa HH, Hameed IH, Mohammed GJ. Analysis of volatile metabolites released by *Staphylococcus aureus* using gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry and determination of its antifungal activity. *Orient J Chem*. 2016; 32(4).

44. Hameed IH, Salman HD, Mohammed GJ. Evaluation of antifungal and antibacterial activity and analysis of bioactive phytochemical compounds of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Cinnamon bark) using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Orient J Chem.* 2016; 32(4).
45. Hameed IH, Jebor MA, Ommer AJ, Abdulzahra AI. Haplotype data of mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 11,719–12,184 and evaluate the importance of these positions for forensic genetic purposes in Iraq. *Mitochondrial DNA.* 2016; 27(2): 1324-1327.
46. Kadhim MJ, Mohammed GJ, Hussein HM. Analysis of bioactive metabolites from *Candida albicans* using (GC-MS) and evaluation of antibacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
47. Mohammad A, Imad H. Autosomal STR: From locus information to next generation sequencing technology. *Research Journal of Biotechnology.* 2013.
48. Hameed, I.H., Abdulzahra, A.I., Jebor, M.A., Kqueen, C.Y., Ommer, A.J. Haplotypes and variable position detection in the mitochondrial DNA coding region encompassing nucleotide positions 10,716-11,184. *Mitochondrial DNA.* 2015.
49. Ubaid JM, Hussein HM, Hameed IH. Analysis of bioactive compounds of *Tribolium castaneum* and evaluation of anti-bacterial activity. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2016; 8(7): 655-670.
50. Altaee N, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Detection of volatile compounds produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from UTI patients by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research.* 2017; 7(6).
51. Altaee N, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Characterization of metabolites produced by *E. coli* and analysis of its chemical compounds using GC-MS. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research.* 2017; 7(6).
52. Hussein JH, Ubaid JM, Hameed IH. Gas chromatography – mass spectrum analysis of volatile components of methanolic leaves extract of *Cordia myxa*. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research.* 2017; 7(6).
53. Kadhim MJ, Kaizal AF, Hameed IH. Medicinal plants used for treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2017; 8(11).
54. Hameed, I.H., Al-Rubaye A.F. and Kadhim, M.J. Antimicrobial Activity of Medicinal Plants and Urinary Tract Infections. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2017; 8(11).
55. Kadhim WA, Kadhim, M.J., Hameed, I.H. Antibacterial Activity of Several Plant Extracts Against *Proteus Species*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2017; 8(11).
56. Kadhim MJ. *In Vitro* antifungal potential of *Acinetobacter baumannii* and determination of its chemical composition by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(19): 657-665.
57. Al-Yaseri A, Kadhim WA, Hameed IH. Detection of volatile compounds emitted by *Proteus mirabilis* isolated from UTI patients and its anti-fungal potential. *Der Pharma Chemica*, 2016; 8(19): 671-678.
58. Ubaid JM, Kadhim MJ, Hameed IH. Study of bioactive methanolic extract of *Camponotus fellah* using Gas chromatography – mass spectrum. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research.* 2017; 7(6).